

Analysis Of Mimicry And Ambivalence In A Model Of Racing Against Fate In A Rubber Plantation By M.H Szekely-Lulofs

Anugrah Yusuf Avriarno
Aqua Culture – IPB University
anugrah.yusuf354@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of the paper analysis is see the impact of colonialism in the form of mimicry and ambivalence in the novel BNdKK by M.H. Szekely-Lulofs researched with the theory of narrative structure and postcolonialism. The theory was applied using descriptive qualitative methods. As a result, from the structure of the novel's storytelling and tracing the history of the Indonesian nation as well as the biographies of the informants, it turns out that this novel is a combination of fictional reality and the historical reality of the life of the colonized geese and the colonizing nation in the Dutch East Indies, especially East Sumatra. Mimicry and ambivalence that occur in the form of language use, culture, and behavior.

Keywords: *mimicry, novel, ambivalence, East Indies*

INTRODUCTION

The novel “Berpacu Nasib di Kebun Karet” (BNdKK) is a novel that describes the practice of Dutch colonialism in Indonesia, especially the plantations of East Sumatra. The superiority of the West as a colonizer was written by the wife of the elite Dutch plantation bureaucracy, Madelon Szekely-Lulofs. He described the impact of Dutch colonialism on the rubber plantation sector. The novel, which was written in Telok Dalam (Asahan Regency, Indonesia) and Budapest (Hungary) from esenber 1929 to June 1931, shocked the Dutch public because of his courage to reveal the cruelty of plantation officials in the midst of the suffering of the people of the Dutch East Indies.

Consequently, the novel as a literary genre has an important position in revealing the reality of human life and the natural surroundings. Novels have great potential to reveal historical reality so as to provide a construction of life in accordance with the human civilization behind the appearance of the novel. In fact, Edward W. Said tested his postcolonial theory by placing the novel as a source of

research data to construct the historical reality of East and West. In his research, Said finds the fact that the fictional reality of the novel in the postcolonial context is closely related to the historical reality of imperialism..

METHOD

This study of analysis uses a descriptive qualitative method because it explains a social event for how the writer us for analyzing the paper. This method is seen by the writer to be very important because this method will show a form of explanation related to a phenomenon that is interpreted in the context and concept of writing. Of course, in carrying out this research, the author uses a hermeneutic approach because this paper anaylis will be studied by exegesis of the contents and adjusting to the events that occurred at that time. As a result, from the structure of the novel's storytelling and tracing the history of the Indonesian nation as well as the biographies of the informants, it turns out that this novel is a combination of fictional reality and the historical reality of the life of the colonized geese and the colonizing nation in the Dutch East Indies, especially East Sumatra. Mimicry and ambivalence that occur in the form of language use, culture, and behavior.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings in this study are the meeting of Western and Eastern civilizations in Indonesia during the reign of the Dutch East Indies caused a clash of civilizations. Ethics and ideal categories of who should be embodied in the meeting between the two cannot be accepted without a fight. Moreover, before a civilization is realized, various views about that civilization have emerged. Therefore, the characters in the novels of the Dutch East Indies face the problem of imitating ethics and ideal categories in society. Ethics and ideal categories are explained by the author in the Dutch East Indies novel. He described westerners as superior humans "because white people never lie, don't steal, and don't cheat". On the other hand, easterners are described, "always slow which is annoying! Always lazy which hurts."

As a superior Dutch nation, it turns out that the characters in the novel BNdKK Frank and John practice mimicry. They adopt characters and behaviors that can adapt to the scene and the time in which the characters are in the story. The innate character of the story character can be lost and replaced with the character where the story character is located. The innate character of the story character can be lost and replaced with the local character of the story character. This was experienced by Frank as a garden assistant in Deli, who Marian as his wife realized had the Dutch East Indies style. This can be seen in the following incident after coming home from work. "You still want to take a shower?" asked marian then frank shook his head and said tomorrow without knowing it for the first time he used the timeless Indian proverb over and over again

The purpose of this analysis of papers in the form of discussions are to find out about ambivalence in fictional reality and historical reality, the BNdKK novel is the result of uncertainty in ethical adjustments and ideal categories. For the colonized nation, the constant appearance of ambivalence will weaken the national identity. Therefore, the potential of the local genius of the colonized nation in the face of ambivalence is a force that requires space and time. Thus, there is a balance in showing the national identity of the colonized nation in front of the colonial nation. Local independence is a form of local genius of plantation communities in East Sumatra. This local independence occurs in the fictional reality and historical reality of “koeli contracts” in the novel BNdKK. Historically, coolies who did not want to return to Java, China, and India chose as free laborers.

In local genius, local independence requires the accuracy of ex-contract workers. This caution was successfully carried out by the former Chinese "contract koeli" who quickly succeeded in trading. On the other hand, other former “contract koeli” have opted for local self-reliance with a variety of businesses. For example, Javanese women choose to become nyai or housemaids and Javanese men choose to open a river crossing boat service business as happened in the fictional reality of the novel BNdKK. With local independence, “contracted keoli” are not dependent on gardeners and are in the same position as gardeners. As the owner of limited power according to the field of business.

CONCLUSION

For how the writer subjectively see from the paper analysis that. In general, the fictional reality that obscures the historical reality of mimicry and ambivalence in the BNdKK novel occurs in different phases. In fact, after calculating the fictional reality data, the life of the elite of the Tumbuk Tinggi plantation bureaucracy takes place in a period of nine years. However, the fictional reality has a historical reality reference that has taken place since the author's first arrival in 1917 and returned to the Netherlands in 1929. The three actors in the story experience mimicry and ambivalence in historical reality as the author's aesthetic experience while in Deli, especially the Telok Dalam Plantation (Asahan District)

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